

at 15 days after transplanting (DT) in an experiment on pest control using the variety ADT 31. Infestation data were taken at 30 DT.

For the stem borer, carbofuran at 0.5 kg a.i./ha effectively reduced deadhearts; increased doses of granules provided no better stem borer control (see table). **W**

Control of stem borer with carbofuran. Aduthurai, India.

Carbofuran 3% G (kg a.i./ha)	Deadhearts/10.8 sq m No.	Transformed value
0.0	83	8.3
0.5	13	3.3
1.0	7	2.5
2.0	6	2.2
C.D. (P = 0.05)		2.5

Effectiveness of root-soaking in insecticides for pest control in paddy

M. Krishnan, G. Varadharajan, S. Kandasamy, and V. K. R. Sathiyandam, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India (adapted from the Aduthurai Reporter)

Four insecticides—chlorpyrifos, cartap, carbofuran, and lindane—were compared

Effectiveness of insecticides and root-soaking durations against deadheart damage caused by stem borers. Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Deadhearts/unit	
	No.	Transformed value
<i>Insecticides</i>		
Chlorpyrifos	11.8	3.9
Cartap	18.6	4.6
Carbofuran	35.8	6.5
Lindane	30.0	5.9
C.D. (P = 0.05)		1.9
<i>Duration of soaking</i>		
With gelatin		
20 min	48.2	6.2
40 min	24.9	4.1
60 min	28.2	5.0
Without gelatin		
20 min	26.5	4.9
40 min	28.0	4.9
60 min	15.4	3.8
Untreated control	53.8	6.9
C.D. (P = 0.05)		1.5

as root-soak treatments at 0.04% concentration with the variety ADT 31 during the 1977 kuruvai (June–Sept). Urea at 1% was digested in the treatment solutions. Gelatin at 6% in treatment solution was compared with no gelatin for root-soaking durations of 20,40, and 60 minutes.

Observations were made at 15 and 30 days after transplanting (DT) for whorl maggot, at 25 DT for jassids, and at 30 DT for stem borer. The treatments did not differ significantly in control of whorl maggot or jassids.

The differences in stem borer control among the four insecticides were statistically significant. Chlorpyrifos and cartap were equally superior to carbofuran and lindane for stem borer control (see table).

Soaking for 20,40, and 60 minutes with and without gelatin produced about equally significant effects. All treatments, except 1 soaking for 20 minutes in gelatin solution, were better than the control. There was no advantage in using gelatin. **W**

Soil and crop management

Paddy straw mat as a nursery bed cover for summer paddy crops

O. P. Meelu, H. S. Sur, and S. Saggar, Department of Soils, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India

Only a single kharif crop of paddy is now grown in the Punjab, but short-duration rice varieties may make a second summer crop of paddy possible. Such a summer crop would have to be transplanted in the second half of April, after the wheat harvest, and nurseries would have to be

sown in February or early March, when the soil temperature is low. This study was undertaken to develop practical technology for raising the soil temperature to improve seed germination and nursery growth.

Conservation of solar heat was compared in four treatments in flat beds (5 × 2 m) and raised beds (8 × 1.5 m) sown on 15 February 1977. In one treatment, the nursery bed was covered with polythene sheet immediately after sowing. The sheet was removed after

A healthy flat bed nursery for summer paddy crops. Punjab Agricultural University, India.